

Studies on the Kinetics of the Oxidation of Leucine with Metaperiodic Acid

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The oxidation of leucine by metaperiodic acid has been studied. The rate was found to be directly proportional to the concentrations of leucine as well as metaperiodic acid. The effect of temperature showed that the Arrhenius equation is valid in this case. The values of the energy of activation, entropy of activation and free energy of activation have been found to be 24.8 K. cal./mole, 2.6 e s u. and 23.9 K. cal./mole respectively.

Studies on the effect of pH showed that the rate constant increases with increasing pH. The probable reactive species are $H_5IO_6^-$ and leucine ions. A suitable mechanism has been proposed for the reaction.

SOME work seems to have been done on the kinetics of the oxidation of leucine by different oxidants¹⁻², but no work has been done on its kinetic studies with metaperiodic acid which has been attempted here.

Experimental

Reagents used: The reagents used were As_2O_3 (0.002M), periodate ($2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$) and leucine ($2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$). The chemicals used were B.D.H. Anala-R. products and were used without any further purification.

Procedure: To 25 ml. 0.02N periodate solution (except in case of use of excess of periodate) was added the requisite quantity of buffer. After keeping it for half an hour in the constant temperature bath, an equivalent quantity (25ml., 0.02N) of leucine (which had been kept at the same temperature of the bath for about half an hour) was added (except in cases of use of excess of leucine) and the volume made upto 100 ml. The timer was started during the mixing. Samples (10 ml.) were removed at known intervals of time and quenched in 25 ml. of 0.002M arsenite solution (0.0033M in case of use of excess of periodate to which 5 ml. of saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate and 1ml.

of 5% KI solution has been added). The excess arsenite was titrated with 0.002M iodine solution (0.0033M. in case of use of excess periodate) after keeping it for 20 minutes, using starch as indicator.

Reaction Rates: The following tables indicate the nature of the results obtained. Graphs were plotted for all results and the specific rate constants k_1 (first order) and k_2 (second order) obtained from the slope of graphs for $\log(a-x)$ and $(1/a-x)$ against time in seconds.

Dependence of Rate on Reductant Concentration: The effect of various concentrations of leucine on the rate was studied in the range $6.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $25.00 \times 10^{-3}M$ and the results showed that the rate is proportional to the concentration of leucine.

Dependence of Rate on Oxidant Concentration: The effect of variation of metaperiodate concentration have been studied in the range $3.57 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $6.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ periodate concentration. The results showed that the rate is proportioned to the periodate concentration.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ADDITION OF DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES

	pH ~ 8.5								
	Iodine = 0.002M								
	Added salt = $25 \times 10^{-3}M$								
	Temperature = $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$								
	Leucine = $1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$								
	Periodate = $2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$								
Salt added	Nil	CH_3COONa	$NaCl$	$NaNO_3$	Na_2SO_4	CH_3COOK	KCl	KNO_3	K_2SO_4
$K. \times 10^{-3}$ litre mole. ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹	3.68	1.90	2.37	3.52	5.40	2.72	2.51	4.13	6.10

